

Nipah virus as an emerging threat: mutational dynamics, pathogenesis, and advances in vaccine development- a systematic review

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ABSTRACT

Nipah virus (NiV) is an emerging zoonotic pathogen with significant pandemic potential. Large outbreaks, such as in Malaysia, required the culling of over one million pigs to control transmission. However, the epidemiology of NiV among animal hosts, including pigs, horses, and bats, remains incompletely understood. NiV infection primarily affects the respiratory and nervous systems, causing severe pneumonia, vasculitis, and meningitis, while encephalitis may be mild or infrequent in some cases. This systematic review summarizes current evidence on NiV mutational variation, pathogenesis, treatment strategies, and vaccine development up to 2022. Data were collected from major databases, including PubMed, PMC, and Cochrane Library. Due to limited therapeutic options, NiV management relies mainly on supportive care, as no approved vaccines or specific antiviral treatments are available for humans or livestock. Preventive strategies focus on reducing zoonotic transmission, particularly by minimizing contact between livestock and bat-contaminated food sources, and improving farm management practices. Early detection and continuous surveillance of high-risk populations and animal reservoirs are essential for outbreak control. Current vaccine research targets viral antigens using subunit and vector-based approaches. Overall, further studies are urgently needed to develop effective vaccines and antiviral therapies for NiV infection.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Emerging and re-emerging zoonotic diseases such as SARS, Ebola, Zika, Nipah, and Hendra virus continue to pose significant global public health challenges [1]. These pathogens originate in animal reservoirs and have the ability to cross species barriers, leading to outbreaks in human populations. Past epidemics, including severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and influenza A (H1N1), demonstrate the potential of zoonotic viruses to trigger widespread health crises and global emergencies [2]. As a result, understanding the transmission dynamics and control of zoonotic diseases has become a critical priority.

Among these emerging pathogens, Nipah virus (NiV) has attracted considerable attention due to its high case fatality rate, which can reach approximately 79% [3]. Since its first identification in Malaysia in 1999, outbreaks have been reported in several countries, particularly in South and Southeast Asia, including Bangladesh and India [3]. The World Health Organization has classified NiV as a priority pathogen because

of its high mortality rate, potential for human-to-human transmission, and the absence of effective vaccines or antiviral therapies [4]. Consequently, NiV is considered a serious threat with pandemic potential (Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of the pandemic situation of the Nipah virus in Asian countries

Year	Country	Location	Number of cases	Number of deaths	Case fatality (%)
Sep 1998 – Apr 1999	Malaysia	Perak, Selangor, Negeri Sembilan	265	105	40
Mar 1999	Singapore	Singapore	11	1	9
Jan – Feb 2001	India	Siliguri	66	45	68
Apr – May 2001	Bangladesh	Meherpur	13	9	69
Jan 2003		Naogaon	12	8	67
Jan 2004		Rajbari	31	23	74
Apr 2004		Faridpur	36	27	75
Jan – Mar 2005		Tangail	12	11	92
Jan – Feb 2007		Thakurgaon	7	3	43
Mar 2007		Kushitia, Pabna, Tatore	8	5	63
Apr 2007		Naogaon	3	1	33
Apr 2007	India	Nadia	5	5	100
Feb 2008	Bangladesh	Manikgon	4	4	100
Apr 2008		Rajbari, Faridpur	7	5	71
Jan 2009		Gaibandha, Rangpur, Nilphamari	3	0	0
Jan 2009		Rajbari	1	1	100
Feb – Mar 2010		Faridpur, Rajbari, Gopalganj, Madaripur	16	14	87.5
		Lalmohirhat, Dinajpur, Comilla, Nilphamari, Rangpur	44	40	91
Feb 2012		Joypurhat, Rajshahi, Tatore, Rajbari, Gopalganj	12	10	83
		Gaibandha, Natore, Rajshahi, Rajbari, Pabna,			87.5
Jan – Feb 2013		Jhenaidah, Mymensingh	24	21	
Feb 2014		Manikganj, Magura, Faridpur, Rangpur, Shaariatpur, Kushitia, Rajshahi, Tatore, Dinajpur, Chapai Nawabganj, Naogaon	18	9	50
Mar – May 2014	Philippines	Tinalon, Midtungok	17	9	53
Feb 2015	Bangladesh	Nilphamari, Pnchoghor, Faridpur, Magura, Naugaon, Rajbari	9	6	67
May 2018	India	Kozhikode, Malappuram	19	17	89
2019	Bangladesh		8	7	87.5
2019	India		1	1	100
2020	Bangladesh		7	5	71.43
2021	Bangladesh		2	0	0
2021	India	Kerala	1	1	100
2022	Bangladesh	Rajshahi	3	2	66.67
2023	Bangladesh	Rajshahi	14	10	71.43
2023	India	Kerala	10	9	90
2024	Bangladesh		5	5	100
2025	India	Kerala	1	1	100
Jan 2026	Bangladesh	Naogaon	1	1	100
Overall Total			786	401	51.02
Malaysia/Philippines/Singapore total			293	115	39.25
Bangladesh total			304	231	75.99
Indian total			109	85	77.98

NiV is a bat-borne virus, with fruit bats recognized as the primary reservoir. Transmission to humans can occur directly or through intermediate hosts, such as pigs, which played a key role in the Malaysian outbreak that resulted in the culling of approximately 1.1 million pigs [5], [6]. The epidemiological factors influencing viral transmission among bats, livestock, and humans remain under investigation [7]. NiV infection primarily affects the respiratory and central nervous systems, causing severe pneumonia, encephalitis, vasculitis, and meningitis. While encephalitis may be mild or infrequent in some cases, vasculitis and meningitis are often severe [8]. Neurological involvement, particularly of the brainstem, is strongly associated with mortality, and survivors may experience long-term neurological complications such as encephalopathy, behavioral abnormalities, and motor dysfunction [7].

Current research has explored various aspects of NiV, including viral genetics, mutational variation, transmission dynamics, and pathogenesis. Diagnostic approaches mainly rely on serological and molecular techniques, while vaccine development has focused on subunit vaccines and viral vector-based platforms targeting key viral antigens. However, no licensed vaccines or specific antiviral treatments are currently available, and patient management remains largely supportive [1]. Preventive strategies primarily aim to

reduce zoonotic transmission by limiting contact between livestock and bat-contaminated food sources, improving farm management practices, and enhancing public awareness [9].

Despite these advances, significant gaps remain in understanding the epidemiological patterns, mutational evolution, and host–pathogen interactions of NiV. In particular, there is a lack of comprehensive integration of viral genetics, disease mechanisms, and translational strategies for vaccine and drug development. These limitations hinder effective preparedness and response to potential outbreaks. Considering these challenges, NiV is increasingly recognized as a potential future pandemic agent [10]. Therefore, this systematic review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of NiV, focusing on mutational variation, pathogenesis, current vaccine development, and treatment approaches. By synthesizing existing evidence, this study seeks to enhance understanding of NiV and support the development of effective prevention and control strategies.

2. METHOD

To perform the systematic review, we followed the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews (PRISMA) standards in four phases: database search, article evaluation, data extraction, and summary. Four writers performed the search for relevant publications, and three authors independently evaluated and extracted data from the articles. Four writers contributed to the final draft, while three authors worked together to assemble the data and perform the systematic review (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Prisma flowchart for Nipah virus scientific literature screening

To learn more about bats and the zoonotic diseases they may spread, including Nipah virus, we looked through articles in PubMed, PMC, and Cochrane. From 1999 to 2022, we looked through all the research publications and reviews that presented data from the field on bat-borne zoonotic diseases, including Nipah virus in Asian and African nations. MeSH terms were used: 'NiV Bangladesh', 'NiV Mutation', 'NiV Pathogenesis', 'NiV Epidemiology', and 'NiV Vaccine'.

For this data extraction, we looked exclusively at scientific reports that included bats and zoonotic illnesses. Information such as the location of the epidemic, the year the sample was taken, the number of people who were tested, the number of people who died, and any potential correlates such as the disease-causing agent, its treatment, and its pathogenicity. were culled from the data.

3. RESULT

3.1. Mutational variations of Nipah virus (NiV)

Mutation is the process by which the likelihood of altering genetic information from one to the next generation, and mutation affects the genetic diversity [11]. To understand the evolution of viruses, it is highly crucial to estimate the rates of viral mutation [12]. In our research regarding Nipah virus, it is one sort of RNA virus which includes an extremely virulent zoonotic illness, and it has the potential for fast spontaneous mutations as like the present COVID-19. Because of its quicker mutation, this virus may quickly adapt to the environment, hosts, or other circumstances, and multiple epidemics happened by the Nipah virus in recent decades. From the following table, we can witness the prior epidemic in Asian countries [13].

Basically, Nipah virus contains two main strains NiV-MY (The Malaysian strain of NiV) and NiV-BD (The Bangladesh strain of NiV) [14]. In addition to, NiV-BD carries the larger genomic size (18,252 nucleotides in length) than NiV-MY (18,246 nucleotides in length) [15]. Because of this greater genomic size, NiV-BD is slightly more pathogenic than NiV-MY, and it spreads interhost transmission more rapidly than NiV-MY [16]. From different studies, it was clinically proven that NiV-BD caused rapid oral shedding and productive infection and a highly infected respiratory tract [17].

Nipah virus transmission occurred rapidly from bats to people in Bangladesh and this occurrence was identified by three ways as like – ingestion of fresh date palm sap, domestic animal and direct contact with NiV infected bat secretions [18]. Besides this, person-to-person transmission also occurred by NiV in Bangladesh and chronic infections were shown in respiratory tract [18]. The transmission happened quickly and acted as like the chain of spreading of NiV. This way, the spreading chain included 5 generations and 34 peoples were infected by this pathogenic virus (NiV) [19]. In the exploration about Nipah virus, two envelop glycoproteins (the receptor binding G proteins and the fusion protein F) are encoded by NiV and the host cell protease activates the viral fusion proteins which is crucial step for viral life cycle [19]. Additionally, trypsin and trypsin-like protease which is similar as like paramyxovirus F proteins with containing monobasic cleavage sites can be activated the fusion protein F [20]. In mutagenesis and structural analysis, G glycoprotein plays a key role for receptor binding and the same thing is not approached in viral ephrin-B2 receptor [14]. However, ephrin-B2 (which is critical of binding NiV) was identified by the performance of alanine-scanning mutagenesis analysis [9]. Further analysis of ephrin-B2, the binding affinity of the mutant receptor with NiV-G (responsible for raising the tendency of infections) was increased by L124A ephrin-B2 mutants [21]. Therefore, L124A mutants gained the ability to support the NiV infection and arranging a new target cell platform [22], [23].

3.2. Pathogenesis of Nipah virus in humans

Non-specific flu-like symptoms such as fever, headache, disorientation, muscle stiffness, and watery stool are common in the early stages of a NiV infection [23]. In certain outbreaks, mild or show no symptoms infections have been documented, but the overall frequency is low and seems to be strain dependant, with the Malaysian variant producing less severe disease, a lower case mortality rate, and a greater proportion of asymptomatic infections than the Bangladesh strain [24]. An encephalitic condition occurs in around 60% of patients after an incubation period of seven to forty days. There is no information on how long it takes for the illness to proceed from the onset of symptoms to the onset of the encephalitic condition. About a third of individuals have neurological symptoms such as meningismus (inflammation of the central nervous system) and seizures. An individual's mental status may deteriorate in as little as seven days (in the case of recent outbreaks in Bangladesh) or as long as 16 days (in general) (Malaysia outbreak). About 20-30% of those who have survived NiV encephalitis have long-term neurologic dysfunction marked by seizures that continue, exhaustion that is incapacitating, and aberrant behavior. In addition, a late-onset or recurring neurological illness may develop in people with initially moderate, non-encephalitic condition. Some patients also have chronic respiratory distress, and respiratory involvement has been more prevalent in the Bangladesh outbreaks than in the Malaysian outbreaks [25].

3.3. Treatment criteria for Nipah virus (NiV) infection

The actual therapy for Nipah virus infection has not yet been developed (drug or vaccination). Supportive therapy, which includes ensuring enough rest, drinking more water, and symptomatic maintenance of acute encephalitis syndrome, is the primary treatment [24]. It is possible to prevent the transmission of this virus from individual to individual by using good nursing procedures. All suspected Nipah virus-infected animals and humans should be quarantined [26]. Infection control techniques should not be replaced by specific pharmaceutical approaches [26]. The intensive care unit is the appropriate setting for monitoring patients who are very unwell. Patients diagnosed with severe pneumonia and acute respiratory failure are required to have mechanical ventilation administered. This incubation phase is thought to last anywhere from three to fourteen days [27].

Fever, headache, dizziness, disorientation, and vomiting are some of the early signs of an infection caused by the Nipah virus. Necrosis of endothelial cells in the vasculature and damage to neural tissue are two of the many adverse effects that may be caused by this virus. Endothelial cells in humans are responsible for vascular permeability; this progressively damages the cell, which results in vessel leakage, and the final outcome is hypovolemic shock. The Nipah virus caused severe symptoms such as encephalitis, convulsions, and coma in those who were infected. However, the epidemic in Malaysia has been linked to a greater number of complications, such as septicemia, intestinal hemorrhage, and renal impairment [28].

In the early stages of Nipah virus infections in Singapore and Malaysia, two medications, ribavirin and acyclovir (Figure 2), were administered to patients. The open-label research in Malaysia indicated that ribavirin reduced mortality by 36% in patients infected with Nipah virus encephalitis, with 45 of 140 patients (32%) in the ribavirin group dying and 29 of 54 (54%) patients developing their symptoms [28], [30]. Serology, histopathology, immunohistochemistry, real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and viral isolation techniques are all laboratory methods for diagnosing Nipah virus infection [28].

Figure 2. Molecular docking representation between acyclovir and Nipah virus fusion glycoprotein. Nipah virus fusion glycoprotein PDB 5EVM (Left), acyclovir docked in binding pocket (Center), acyclovir interaction with 5EVM (Right)

For Nipah virus infection, the dose form of ribavirin has not yet been specified, however during the first stage, WHO recommends Lassa fever dosage amounts of 30mg/kg for children and 2000 mg/kg for adults, with a maintenance period of roughly 10 days [25]. It is possible to administer ribavirin orally since it does not bind to plasma protein. Ribavirin's side effects include neutropenia (80%-40%), anemia (11%-35%), lymphocytopenia (12%-14%), and the potential for suicidal thoughts.

However, ribavirin has not been shown to be teratogenic in humans but has been reported to be teratogenic in mice and rabbits (Table 2) [29]-[39]. Ribavirin has a lengthy half-life; thus, it must be taken at least seven months before pregnancy to be safe [36]. The short-term safety profile of Ribavirin is impressive, given its promising in-vivo and in-vitro results. Although a controlled study is missing, the status is still unresolved. When it comes to treating nipah virus infection, Ribavirin was recommended without reservation [27]. A study in animals found that ribavirin therapy delayed mortality from hamster infection by around five days, but it did not deter demise. The antimalarial medicinal agent chloroquine works in vitro in a manner similar to ribavirin. For this reason, chloroquine and ribavirin were tested in a golden hamster model for the treatment of Nipah virus infection [27].

3.3.1. Monoclonal antibody

An antibody that targets the ephrin-B2 and ephrin-B3 receptors, which are neutralized by the antibody in vitro through binding with the area of the Henipavirus G envelope glycoprotein. Nipah virus may

be prevented in ferrets by this antibody [36]. In a research, m102.4 protected African green monkeys against infection and death after the injection of a fatal amount (AGM) [37].

Table 2. Drugs with potential antiviral activity

Drug molecule	Description	Experimental model	Reference
Favipiravir	Purine analogue	In vitro (Syrian hamster)	[29]
Ribavirin	Guanosine analogue	In vitro	[30]
Acyclovir	Guanosine analogue	Historical review	[31]
Remdesivir (GS-5734)	Adenosine analogue	In vitro (African green monkey)	[32], [33]
Balapiravir (R ₁₄₁₉)	Cytidine analogue	In vitro	[34]
Chloroquinine	4-aminoquinoline	In vitro	[35]
Poly (D)- Poly (C ₁₂ U)	Interferon inducer	In vitro (Hamster)	[36]
Human mAb m102.4	G glycoprotein fusion inhibitor	Ferrets (African green monkey)	[37]
Human mAb h5B3.1	F glycoprotein fusion inhibitor	Ferrets	[38], [39]

3.3.2. Favipiravir

An RNA polymerase inhibitor for viral RNA. Favipiravir is an antiviral drug designed to keep influenza at bay. Nipah virus infection in Syrian hamsters may be reduced or inhibited by the use of the antiviral favipiravir drug [40]. In an emergency, anti-G and anti-F monoclonal antibodies are often employed in India. Only if the RT-PCR test is negative on a throat swab or blood sample may the patient be discharged. And it's not clear how long it will last, but we may presume that it will last for 21 days. After the infection has been confirmed, released patients are encouraged to remain in isolation for a minimum of 21 days [29].

The primary component of therapy for a NiV infection is palliative care, which may include the administration of anticonvulsants, the administration of fluids, the treatment of secondary infections, and mechanical ventilation [29]. There are presently no medicines that are authorized that can be used in humans that are effective in treating NiV infection. During the NiV Malaysia epidemic in 1998-1999, the antiviral medication ribavirin was given to 140 patients, which resulted in a 36 percent decrease in death when compared to the mortality rate of 52 control patients who were not treated [29]. On the other hand, the medication distribution was not done in a random way; there is a possibility that the patients who were treated had superior care in general. This makes the result difficult to predict. Subsequent animal challenge trials conducted in hamsters revealed that ribavirin, although it did not prevent mortality after NiV infection, did postpone the onset of the disease. After transmission of African Green Monkeys with the similarly related Hendra Virus (HeV; see also Hendra Virus), researchers found comparable results [65].

4. CURRENT STATE OF NIPAH VIRUS VACCINE (NIV) DEVELOPMENT

Undoubtedly, Nipah virus is an emerging, unapparent & mild disease, but there is no approved vaccine for humans or any livestock. The approach of the NiV vaccine focused on antigens that are delivered as subunit vaccines or using viral vectors (Table 3) [41]-[55]. Nowadays, the most studied vaccine participant is the soluble form of the G protein that is highly related to the Hinda virus [56]. But currently, there are no drugs or vaccines for the Nipah virus Research and Development Blueprint. They advise treating severe respiratory and neurologic complications [57]. Although NiV is an infectious & pathogenic disease, there is no licensed human vaccine; there is potent proof that an effective vaccine is feasible. The recent evidence suggests that the average incubation period for Niv is above the 5-7 days' threshold, and so has a strong potential for the development of a successful vaccine [58].

Vaccine developed by Auro Vaccine and Public Health Vaccines is the first in the world to reach clinical trial. All R&D activities for NiV vaccines are in the pre-clinical stage, having been tested in the hamster, ferret, and/or AGM preclinical challenge models (Table 4, see in Appendix) [2], [3], [59]-[65]. Suggestion by a number of factors suggest that developing a safe and effective human prophylactic vaccine against NiV is scientifically possible. There is a broad agreement that neutralizing antibodies confer protection against NiV infection [66]. The pigs suffered during the Malaysian outbreak caused by the NiV virus. The severity of symptoms of NiV infections in pig differ with age. An adjuvanted Hev SG protein subunit-based vaccine has been licensed in Australia to protect horses against Hev and to reduce the zoonotic risk to humans. But unfortunately, this vaccine failed to treat pigs from experimental challenge with NiV [67].

Among all studies of various animals, during initial studies, mice were found to be highly resistant to infection with NiV. Recently, two mouse models were given for the experiment [50]. According to that experiment, it showed that aged animals are susceptible to NiV infection via the intranasal route. So far, vaccine research has concentrated on the viral F and G envelope glycoproteins, either produced in recombinant virus or subunit immunogens, to protect against the henipavirus.

The immunogen HeV recombinant soluble G glycoprotein (sG) has also been used in many research studies (HeVsG). Cats were able to withstand a deadly NiV challenge with no clinical indications, and the results indicated that this animal model had developed a sterilizing immunity. Reisolated virus was found in the brains of six cats that had received the second greatest doses of vaccination, or viral RNA was found in the brains of one vaccinated cat.

PHV02 is an Rvsv vector vaccine candidate expressing the Nipah virus glycoprotein in the Bangladesh strain of Nipah virus vaccine (PHV02). It is a live, attenuated Rvsv vector vaccine candidate. It will also be used to find the development of critical research tools, such as assays and antibody standards, for forthcoming Phase II clinical trials of Nipah vaccinations, which are presently expected to begin in mid-to-late 2022. At this time, the field considers the ferret and AGM models to be the most appropriate animal models for reproducing henipavirus infection and illness, as well as for the assessment of novel anti-henipavirus treatments and vaccines. In earlier research, the authors and others, including others, have put the HeV-sG recombinant subunit immunogen through its paces as a potential vaccine candidate in cats, ferrets, horses, and other animal models of the disease [68].

Table 3. Animals tested NiV vaccine candidates

Reference	Vaccine description	Animal(s) immunized	Vaccination route/Regimen/Challenge (Strain3)	NiV neutralization titers (Pre-challenge) ²
[41]	Vaccinia virus (VV) vector expressing NiV G or F	Hamsters	SC/2 vaccinations 1 month apart/challenge 3 months after last vaccination (M)	~ 1:10 – 1:25
[42]	Canarypox vector (ALVAC) expressing NiV G or F	Pigs	IM/2 vaccinations 14 days apart/challenge on day 28 post 2nd vaccination (NiV strain not specified)	1:200 – 1:1280
[43]	Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) expressing NiV G or F	Mice	Footpad inoculation/3 vaccinations on week 0, 5 and 18/no challenge	~ 1:215 – 1:217 *
[44]	Newcastle disease virus (NDV) vector expressing NiV F or G	Pigs	IM/2 vaccinations 4 weeks apart/no challenge	~ 1:27 – 1:212*
[45]	Single-cycle replication VSV-ΔG vector expressing NiV G or F	Ferrets	IM/one vaccination/challenge on day 20 post-vaccination (M).	~1:40 – 1:160
[46]	Adeno-associated virus (AAV) vector expressing NiV G	Hamsters	IM/one vaccination/challenge at 5 weeks post-vaccination (M).	< 1:10 to 1:160
[47]	Measles virus vaccine vector expressing NiV G glycoprotein	Hamsters, AGM*	Hamster: IP/2 vaccinations 21 days apart/challenge 7 days post 2nd Vaccination AGM. SC/2 vaccinations 28 days apart/challenge 2 weeks post 2nd vaccination (NiV strain not specified).	Hamster: Not reported AGM: 1:1600 – 1:3200
[48]	Replication-competent VSV vector expressing NiV G or F	Hamsters	IP/one vaccination/challenge on day 28 post-vaccination (M).	1:80 - ≥ 1:640
[49]	Replication-defective VSV-ΔG vector expressing NiV G or F.	Hamsters	IM/ one vaccination/challenge at day 32 post-vaccination (M)	~ 5 x10 ³ – 1 x 10 ⁴
[50]	Canarypox vector (ALVAC) expressing HeV G or F	Ponies (horses)	IM/2 vaccinations 21 days apart/ no challenge	~ 1:2128*
[51]	Live-attenuated VSV vector expressing NiV G	AGM1	IM/one vaccination/challenge on day 29 post-vaccination (M).	1:80 – 1:160
[52]	Live attenuated VSV vector expressing NiV G	Hamsters	IP/one vaccination/challenge one day post- vaccination (100% survival) (M).	Not reported
[53]	Live-attenuated rabies virus vaccine vector (RABV) expressing NiV G	Mice	IM/2 vaccinations 28 days apart/no challenge	~1:10 to 1:600 (no challenge)
[54]	Single-cycle replication VSV-ΔG vector expressing NiV G or F	AGM1	IM/one vaccination/challenge on day 28 post-vaccination (B).	1:160 – 1:640
[55]	Chimpanzee adenovirus (ChAd) vector expressing NiV G	Hamsters	IM/one or two vaccinations (28 days apart)/challenge 70 days post-prime or 42 days post- boost (M and B).	~1:40 - ~1:100

5. CONCLUSION

Nipah virus (NiV) remains a significant emerging zoonotic pathogen with substantial pandemic potential. Accumulating evidence suggests that NiV is capable of adapting to new host species and transmission pathways beyond its primary reservoir, *Pteropus* fruit bats. Since its initial identification, NiV has demonstrated the ability to spread to humans through contact with infected animals, particularly pigs, as well as through human-to-human transmission. Repeated spillover events and subsequent human transmission may substantially increase the overall disease burden, highlighting the importance of controlling both zoonotic and interpersonal transmission pathways. Despite efforts to reduce exposure through physical and environmental interventions, the risk of NiV transmission persists, particularly in regions with close interactions between humans, livestock, and wildlife. Current research demonstrates promising progress in vaccine development, with several candidate vaccines showing efficacy in animal models such as hamsters, ferrets, and African green monkeys. These models have been instrumental in replicating key features of human NiV infection and pathogenesis. In addition, advances in immunological assays and the identification of neutralizing antibodies are expected to support the establishment of correlates of protection, although assay standardization remains in its early stages. However, significant challenges remain in translating these findings into effective human interventions. There are currently no licensed vaccines or specific antiviral therapies for NiV, and treatment remains largely supportive. Therefore, the development of safe and effective vaccines and antiviral agents is urgently needed. In parallel, strengthening public health strategies—such as surveillance of high-risk populations, improved livestock management, and community education on hygiene and zoonotic transmission—is essential to reduce the risk of future outbreaks. In conclusion, a comprehensive and integrated approach combining biomedical research, vaccine development, and public health interventions is critical to mitigate the threat posed by NiV. Continued interdisciplinary research and global collaboration will be essential to enhance preparedness and prevent future epidemics.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data availability does not apply to this paper as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

APPENDIX

Table 4. NiV submits animal-tried vaccine candidates

Reference	Vaccine description	Animal(s) immunized	Vaccination route/Regimen/Challenge (Strains)	NiV Neutralization Titers (Pre-challenge) ²
[59]	SGNiV or sGHeV adjuvanted with Montanide/QuilA/DEAE dextran	Cats	SC/3 vaccinations 2 weeks apart/challenge 15 weeks after the first vaccination (M).	1:2560-1:20480
[60]	Recombinant soluble HeVG glycoprotein adjuvanted with CpG + AlhydrogelTM	Cats	IM/ 2 vaccinations 21 days apart/challenge on day 42 post 1st vaccination (M).	1:32-1:512
[61]	Virus like particles (VLPs) comprising NiV M, G and F	Mice	SC/ 3 vaccinations on days 0, 15 and 29/no challenge	1:5->1:80
[62]	Recombinant soluble HeVG glycoprotein adjuvanted with CpG + AlhydrogelTM	AGM1	IM/ 2 vaccinations 21 days apart/challenge 21 days post 2nd vaccination (M).	1:67-1:379
[63]	Recombinant soluble HeVG glycoprotein adjuvanted with CpG	Ferrets	SC/2 vaccinations 20 days apart/challenge 20 days or 14 months post 2nd vaccination (B)	1:16-1:128
[64]	Recombinant soluble HeV G glycoprotein in a proprietary adjuvant (Zoetis, Inc.)	Pigs	IM/ 2 vaccinations 21 days apart/challenge 35 days post 1st vaccination (Strain not specified)	1:25-1:450
[65]	Virus-like particles (VLPs) containing NiVM, F and G	Hamsters	Single dose trial: TM/ one dose/challenge on day 28 post vaccination (M) 3 dose trial: 3 doses on days 0, 21 and 42/challenge on days 58 (M).	3-dose trial 1:200-1:2500 2-dose trial 1:10-1:200

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Devnath and H. M. A. A. Masud, "Nipah virus: a potential pandemic agent in the context of the current severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 pandemic," *New Microbes and New Infections*, vol. 41, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.nmni.2021.100873.
- [2] S. P. Luby, "The pandemic potential of nipah virus," *Antiviral Research*, vol. 100, no. 1, pp. 38–43, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2013.07.011.
- [3] R. K. Ochani, S. Batra, A. Shaikh, and A. Asad, "Nipah virus the rising epidemic: a review," *Infezioni in Medicina*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 117–127, 2019.
- [4] K. Skowron *et al.*, "Nipah virus—another threat from the world of zoonotic viruses," *Frontiers in Microbiology*, vol. 12, 2022, doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.811157.
- [5] N. Hauser, A. C. Gushiken, S. Narayanan, S. Kottilil, and J. V. Chua, "Evolution of nipah virus infection: past, present, and future considerations," *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 24, 2021, doi: 10.3390/tropicalmed6010024.
- [6] D. D. Kulkarni, C. Tosh, G. Venkatesh, and D. Senthil Kumar, "Nipah virus infection: current scenario," *Indian Journal of Virology*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 398–408, 2013, doi: 10.1007/s13337-013-0171-y.
- [7] R. K. Singh *et al.*, "Nipah virus: epidemiology, pathology, immunobiology and advances in diagnosis, vaccine designing and control strategies—a comprehensive review," *Veterinary Quarterly*, vol. 39, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1080/01652176.2019.1580827.
- [8] K. T. Wong, "Emerging nipah virus encephalitis and its modeling," *BMC Proceedings*, vol. 2, no. S1, p. 43, 2008, doi: 10.1186/1753-6561-2-s1-s43.
- [9] B. S. P. Ang, T. C. C. Lim, and L. Wang, "Nipah virus infection," *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, vol. 56, no. 6, 2018, doi: 10.1128/JCM.01875-17.
- [10] V. Sharma, S. Kaushik, R. Kumar, J. P. Yadav, and S. Kaushik, "Emerging trends of nipah virus: a review," *Reviews in Medical Virology*, vol. 29, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1002/rmv.2010.
- [11] R. Sanjuán and P. Domingo-Calap, "Mechanisms of viral mutation," *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, vol. 73, no. 23, pp. 4433–4448, 2016, doi: 10.1007/s00018-016-2299-6.
- [12] R. Sanjuán, M. R. Nebot, N. Chirico, L. M. Mansky, and R. Belshaw, "Viral mutation rates," *Journal of Virology*, vol. 84, no. 19, pp. 9733–9748, 2010, doi: 10.1128/jvi.00694-10.
- [13] E. B. Yahya, A. M. Alqadhi, M. A. Abdulsamad, and A. A. Allaq, "Asian nipah virus and the potential of new pandemic," *Pakistan Journal of Biotechnology*, vol. 18, no. (1-2), 2021, doi: 10.34016/pjbt.2021.18.1.17.
- [14] L. M. Looi and K. B. Chua, "Lessons from the Nipah virus outbreak in Malaysia," *The Malaysian Journal of Pathology*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 63–67, 2007.
- [15] M. S. Chadha *et al.*, "Nipah virus-associated encephalitis outbreak, Siliguri, India," *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 235–240, 2006, doi: 10.3201/eid1202.051247.
- [16] E. S. Gurley *et al.*, "Person-to-person transmission of nipah virus in a bangladeshi community," *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 1031–1037, 2007, doi: 10.3201/eid1307.061128.
- [17] V. P. Hsu *et al.*, "Nipah virus encephalitis reemergence, Bangladesh," *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, vol. 10, no. 12, pp. 2082–2087, 2004, doi: 10.3201/eid1012.040701.
- [18] S. Chowdhury *et al.*, "Serological evidence of henipavirus exposure in cattle, goats and pigs in Bangladesh," *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, vol. 8, no. 11, 2014, doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0003302.
- [19] ICDDR,B, "Nipah outbreak in faridpur district, Bangladesh, 2010," *Health Science Bulletin*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2010.
- [20] M. K. Verma, P. Verma, S. Singh, P. Gaur, A. H. Siddiqui, and S. Pandey, "Nipah virus- infectious agent: an overview," *International Journal of Life-Sciences Scientific Research*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 1844–1850, 2018, doi: 10.21276/ijlssr.2018.4.3.16.
- [21] S. P. Luby, E. S. Gurley, and M. J. Hossain, "Transmission of human infection with Nipah virus," *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, vol. 49, no. 11, pp. 1743–1748, 2009, doi: 10.1086/647951.

- [22] S. Diederich, E. Dietzel, and A. Maisner, "Nipah virus fusion protein: influence of cleavage site mutations on the cleavability by cathepsin I, trypsin and furin," *Virus Research*, vol. 145, no. 2, pp. 300–306, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.virusres.2009.07.020.
- [23] J. Yu, G. Marsh, D. Khetawat, C. C. Broder, L. F. Wang, and Z. Shi, "Mutations in the g-h loop region of ephrin-b2 can enhance nipah virus binding and infection," *Journal of General Virology*, vol. 92, no. 9, pp. 2142–2151, 2011, doi: 10.1099/vir.0.033787-0.
- [24] M. K. Lo *et al.*, "Potent in vitro activity of $\beta\beta$ -d-4'-chloromethyl-2'-deoxy-2'-fluorocytidine against nipah virus," *Antiviral Research*, vol. 175, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2020.104712.
- [25] M. L. Grayson *et al.*, *Kucers' the use of antibiotics: a clinical review of antibacterial, antifungal, antiparasitic, and antiviral drugs, seventh edition*. Florida, USA: CRC Press, 2017. doi: 10.1201/9781498747967.
- [26] A. R. Thorner and R. Dolin, "Henipaviruses," in *Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases*, 8th ed., vol. 2, 2015, pp. 1974–1980. doi: 10.1016/B978-1-4557-4801-3.00163-6.
- [27] J. R. Ryan, "Containing and preventing biological threats," in *Biosecurity and Bioterrorism*, 2nd ed., 2016, pp. 113–134. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-802029-6.00005-0.
- [28] O. L. Laskin *et al.*, "Ribavirin disposition in high-risk patients for acquired immunodeficiency syndrome," *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 546–555, 1987, doi: 10.1038/clpt.1987.70.
- [29] B. E. Dawes *et al.*, "Favipiravir (t-705) protects against Nipah virus infection in the hamster model," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 7604, May 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-25780-3.
- [30] M. K. Lo *et al.*, "GS-5734 and its parent nucleoside analog inhibit filo-, pneumo-, and paramyxoviruses," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 43395, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1038/srep43395.
- [31] A. Tamin, B. H. Harcourt, T. G. Ksiazek, P. E. Rollin, W. J. Bellini, and P. A. Rota, "Functional properties of the fusion and attachment glycoproteins of nipah virus," *Virology*, vol. 296, pp. 190–200, 2002, doi: 10.1006/viro.2002.1418.
- [32] T. W. Geisbert *et al.*, "A single dose investigational subunit vaccine for human use against Nipah virus and hendra virus," *npj Vaccines*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41541-021-00284-w.
- [33] M. K. Lo *et al.*, "Remdesivir (gs-5734) protects african green monkeys from Nipah virus challenge," *Science Translational Medicine*, 2019, doi: 10.1126/scitranslmed.aau9242.
- [34] A. L. Hotard, B. He, S. T. Nichol, C. F. Spiropoulou, and M. K. Lo, "40-azidocytidine (r1479) inhibits henipaviruses and other paramyxoviruses with high potency," *Antiviral Research*, vol. 144, pp. 147–152, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2017.06.011.
- [35] A. N. Freiberg, M. N. Worthy, B. Lee, and M. R. Holbrook, "Combined chloroquine and ribavirin treatment does not prevent death in a hamster model of Nipah and hendra virus infection," *Journal of General Virology*, vol. 91, no. 3, pp. 765–772, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1099/vir.0.017269-0.
- [36] M. C. Georges-Courbot *et al.*, "Poly(i)-poly(c12u) but not ribavirin prevents death in a hamster model of nipah virus infection," *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, vol. 50, no. 5, pp. 1768–1772, 2006, doi: 10.1128/AAC.50.5.1768-1772.2006.
- [37] K. N. Bossart *et al.*, "A neutralizing human monoclonal antibody protects against lethal disease in a new ferret model of acute nipah virus infection," *PLoS Pathogens*, vol. 5, no. 10, 2009, doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1000642.
- [38] T. W. Geisbert *et al.*, "Therapeutic treatment of nipah virus infection in nonhuman primates with a neutralizing human monoclonal antibody," *Science Translational Medicine*, vol. 6, 2014, doi: 10.1126/scitranslmed.3008929.
- [39] C. E. Mire *et al.*, "A cross-reactive humanized monoclonal antibody targeting fusion glycoprotein function protects ferrets against lethal nipah virus and hendra virus infection," *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, vol. 221, 2020, doi: 10.1093/infdis/jiz515.
- [40] K. N. Bossart *et al.*, "Infectious disease: a neutralizing human monoclonal antibody protects african green monkeys from hendra virus challenge," *Science Translational Medicine*, vol. 3, no. 105, 2011, doi: 10.1126/scitranslmed.3002901.
- [41] V. Guillaume *et al.*, "Nipah virus: vaccination and passive protection studies in a hamster model," *Journal of Virology*, vol. 78, no. 2, pp. 834–840, 2004, doi: 10.1128/jvi.78.2.834-840.2004.
- [42] H. M. Weingartl *et al.*, "Recombinant nipah virus vaccines protect pigs against challenge," *Journal of Virology*, vol. 80, no. 16, pp. 7929–7938, 2006, doi: 10.1128/jvi.00263-06.
- [43] G. N. Defang, D. Khetawat, C. C. Broder, and G. V. Quinlan, "Induction of neutralizing antibodies to hendra and nipah glycoproteins using a Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus in vivo expression system," *Vaccine*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 212–220, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2010.10.053.
- [44] D. Kong *et al.*, "Newcastle disease virus-vectored nipah encephalitis vaccines induce b and t cell responses in mice and long-lasting neutralizing antibodies in pigs," *Virology*, vol. 432, no. 2, pp. 327–335, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.virol.2012.06.001.
- [45] C. E. Mire *et al.*, "Single injection recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus vaccines protect ferrets against lethal nipah virus disease," *Virology Journal*, vol. 10, 2013, doi: 10.1186/1743-422X-10-353.
- [46] A. Ploquin *et al.*, "Protection against henipavirus infection by use of recombinant adeno-associated virus-vector vaccines," *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, vol. 207, no. 3, pp. 469–478, 2013, doi: 10.1093/infdis/jis699.
- [47] M. Yoneda *et al.*, "Recombinant measles virus vaccine expressing the nipah virus glycoprotein protects against lethal nipah virus challenge," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2013, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0058414.
- [48] B. L. DeBuysscher, D. Scott, A. Marzi, J. Prescott, and H. Feldmann, "Single-dose live-attenuated nipah virus vaccines confer complete protection by eliciting antibodies directed against surface glycoproteins," *Vaccine*, vol. 32, no. 22, pp. 2637–2644, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2014.02.087.
- [49] M. K. Lo *et al.*, "Single-dose replication-defective vsv-based nipah virus vaccines provide protection from lethal challenge in syrian hamsters," *Antiviral Research*, vol. 101, no. 1, pp. 26–29, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2013.10.012.
- [50] V. Guillaume-Vasselin *et al.*, "Protection from hendra virus infection with canarypox recombinant vaccine," *npj Vaccines*, vol. 1, 2016, doi: 10.1038/npjvaccines.2016.3.
- [51] J. Prescott *et al.*, "Single-dose live-attenuated vesicular stomatitis virus-based vaccine protects African green monkeys from Nipah virus disease," *Vaccine*, vol. 33, no. 24, pp. 2823–2829, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2015.03.089.
- [52] B. L. Debuysscher, D. Scott, T. Thomas, H. Feldmann, and J. Prescott, "Peri-exposure protection against Nipah virus disease using a single-dose recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus-based vaccine," *npj Vaccines*, vol. 1, 2016, doi: 10.1038/npjvaccines.2016.2.
- [53] R. Keshwara *et al.*, "Rabies-based vaccine induces potent immune responses against nipah virus," *npj Vaccines*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41541-019-0109-5.
- [54] C. E. Mire *et al.*, "Use of single-injection recombinant vesicular stomatitis virus vaccine to protect nonhuman primates against lethal nipah virus disease," *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 1144–1152, 2019, doi: 10.3201/eid2506.181620.
- [55] N. van Doremalen *et al.*, "A single-dose chadox1-vectored vaccine provides complete protection against nipah bangladesh and malaysia in syrian golden hamsters," *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, vol. 13, no. 6, J2019, doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0007462.
- [56] R. K. McLean and S. P. Graham, "Vaccine development for nipah virus infection in pigs," *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, vol. 6, no. FEB, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fvets.2019.00016.
- [57] World Health Organization, "Nipah virus." 2018.

- [58] B. A. Satterfield, B. E. Dawes, and G. N. Milligan, "Status of vaccine research and development of vaccines for Nipah virus," *Vaccine*, vol. 34, no. 26, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2015.12.075.
- [59] B. A. Mungall *et al.*, "Feline model of acute nipah virus infection and protection with a soluble glycoprotein-based subunit vaccine," *Journal of Virology*, vol. 80, no. 24, pp. 12293–12302, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1128/JVI.01619-06.
- [60] J. A. McEachern *et al.*, "A recombinant subunit vaccine formulation protects against lethal nipah virus challenge in cats," *Vaccine*, vol. 26, no. 31, pp. 3842–3852, Jul. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2008.05.016.
- [61] P. Walpita, J. Barr, M. Sherman, C. F. Basler, and L. Wang, "Vaccine potential of nipah virus-like particles," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 6, no. 4, p. e18437, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0018437.
- [62] K. N. Bossart *et al.*, "A hendra virus g glycoprotein subunit vaccine protects african green monkeys from nipah virus challenge," *Science Translational Medicine*, vol. 4, no. 146, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.1126/scitranslmed.3004241.
- [63] J. A. Pallister *et al.*, "Vaccination of ferrets with a recombinant g glycoprotein subunit vaccine provides protection against nipah virus disease for over 12 months," *Virology Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 237, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1186/1743-422X-10-237.
- [64] B. S. Pickering *et al.*, "Protection against henipaviruses in swine requires both, cell-mediated and humoral immune response," *Vaccine*, vol. 34, no. 40, pp. 4777–4786, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2016.08.028.
- [65] P. Walpita *et al.*, "A vlp-based vaccine provides complete protection against nipah virus challenge following multiple-dose or single-dose vaccination schedules in a hamster model," *npj Vaccines*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 21, 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41541-017-0023-7.
- [66] B. Rockx, "Recent developments in experimental animal models of henipavirus infection," *Pathogens and Disease*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 197–204, 2014, doi: 10.1111/2049-632X.12149.
- [67] Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations, "Nipah survivors study to advance new vaccines against highly fatal threat." 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.icddr.org/news-and-events/press-corner/press-releases?id=121>
- [68] H. Weingartl, "Hendra and nipah viruses: pathogenesis, animal models and recent breakthroughs in vaccination," *Vaccine: Development and Therapy*, p. 59, 2015, doi: 10.2147/vdt.s86482.

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